

Pioneering AI in MLTC: Bridging Research and Practice

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The
Alan Turing
Institute

Swansea
University
Prifysgol
Abertawe

Population Data Science
Gwyddor Data Poblogaeth

Focussing on the future:

How do we ensure impact through translation of your research to improve health & social care for MLTC patients, in the next 5 years?

The workshop logistics

The workshop was designed to provide members of the AIM community with an opportunity to discuss key topics shaping the future of AI and MLTC research, aiming to improve lives for those living with or caring for people with Multiple Long-Term Conditions. In collaboration with NIHR, six discussion topics with guiding questions were prepared to explore challenges and potential solutions.

The event welcomed 80-100 registered attendees, with 12-16 participants engaging in discussions on each topic and eight joining online. A one-hour session included 50 minutes for discussion, focusing on capturing attendees' insights and identifying three key takeaways for feedback.

There were 7 topics discussed in the workshop, this summary includes the discussion and takeaway from the 2nd topic.

- **Topic 1: How can we mobilise knowledge that has been generated by AIM?**
- **Topic 2: What are the strategies & good practices for engaging and sustaining patient communities?**
- **Topic 3: How can we champion early career researchers in MLTC research?**
- **Topic 4: What technical support is needed for the next stage of translation/impact?**
- **Topic 5: Who do we need to engage to ensure broad collaboration for translating research?**
- **Topic 6: How would we move towards system thinking and transdisciplinary research in MLTC?**
- **Topic 7: What are the strategies & good practices for engaging and sustaining patient communities?**

Topic 2: What are the strategies & good practices for engaging and sustaining patient communities?

Chaired and Scribed by: Ali Drewett and Sarah Rabbitte

The key takeaways

1. Valuing PPI - funding decisions, time, and continuity over the long term.
2. Accessibility - Language and pacing - accessibility, easy reading and personalisation. Creative dissemination - posters, papers and academic talks.
3. Embedding PPI involvement throughout the projects - decide the content and not just make the content accessible. Part of a team.

Recommendations for MLTC funders

1. Develop a better PPI payment framework:
 - Work with government to create clear guidance on payment options that don't affect benefits
 - Establish flexible payment mechanisms (including both digital and physical vouchers)
 - Create standardised processes for paying carers and backfill
 - Institutions should have a better administrative procedure for PPI payments
 - Set appropriate rates that reflect expertise and time commitment
2. Create an inclusive engagement toolkit:
 - Fund development of creative engagement materials (videos, posters, role-play resources)
 - Support translation services for key communities
 - Provide researcher training on inclusive communication
 - Establish mentoring programmes to support new PPI members
 - Resource community-based engagement activities
 - Enable long-term relationship building with diverse communities

Summary of all the discussion

- Communication needs to be all-inclusive and lay people have to feel that they're valued
- Regular feedback needs to be provided - needs to be 2 way
- Support:
 - The PPI needs training to access what the research is about. It helps PPI to know why decisions have been made.

- Support needs to be costed in at the planning stage
- Language spoken or written needs to be consistent as it spreads over a wide audience. Plan english. People can revert to medical jargon without thinking. There is a mismatch between general language and medical language, there is a mismatch about meaning
- I don't think that people do it on purpose but you need to understand how to communicate to people who don't know about research. Training comes into this but training is not just for PPI members it should be for researchers too. PPI need to edit documents
- A good researcher is someone who knows how to talk to a person with a learning disability but researchers need to know this. A visual system can help i.e. red - I need to help. We made 3 pages of notes today to explain what complicated words mean i.e. demographics, longitudinal, granular. These words don't make sense.
- I think someone who listens to us makes a good researcher. Good eye contact, body language. Animations can help with this too.
- Diversity:
 - We need to widen the net as far as we possibly can.
 - We need to access those various communities physically. If you don't, barriers can arise. Barriers include travel, not being able to catch the bus.
 - There needs to be a targeted approach i.e. age ranges, ethnicity, and people who are actually interested in research. Sometimes we need to reassure people that research is not scary and that you don't need to be a scientist to participate, you have value!
 - Reassure people by going into their community, have a coffee, get to know people first. It takes time and it's a gradual approach. Get to know people and add in the research element. Need to build trust and then start to talk about the research
 - You do have to be careful though as people think you have a hidden agenda
 - You need to really understand that culture rules and abide by these
 - We did a crafts session and decorated tote bags. People preferred this but we also talked about research
 - Sometimes you need to be straight with people, they might prefer this. You do need to determine the approach in advance. Elderly people are particularly difficult to engage with.
 - Sometimes the same people are getting involved all of the time. You need to be creative to get more people.
 - It's key to showcase people's value. Also, get people at an early stage of their career i.e. student nurses to let them know about research early on

- Payments are a big issue. People should be re-numerated for their time. It's an important aspect of inclusion. It is a resource that is needed and researchers need to learn about the importance of payments. It can be tokenistic i.e. £5 voucher for 2 hours of their time. If people are 'experts' this needs to be reflected. An agreement needs to be included from the start.
- Benefit restrictions need to be considered. It's very scary for some people thinking their benefits will be stopped. Not everyone wants an Amazon voucher. There is diversity in what people want. I had to go out and buy vouchers with my own money and claim this back. I shouldn't have to do this. There are institutional-level considerations that need to be looked at. There is no guidance. What should we pay research participants and PPI members? Different/the same. How do we pay carers? If they are at work do we pay people twice? Backfill offers are not taken up. NIHR need to provide CLEAR guidance. The time people commit can add up and NIHR needs to work out a system with the government about what people can accept. You are excluding a large body of people who can't accept payments but should be able to. Some people want physical vouchers and not e-vouchers. Can never have cash. Organisations are not set up to offer varied payment options. A lot of paperwork is required. Why can't universities treat us like staff and make less paperwork
- NIHR have 2 paragraphs of guidance. 'Ask the job centre'. Anything offered through a government needs to be tax-exempt.
- How can it not exacerbate health inequalities?
 - Hiat qnaire - is the project going to tackle health inequalities. On the old CLAHRC. School for Public Health Research.
 - For equity Website - includes going the extra mile. Equity and Equality. Need to be making the right reasonable adjustments. Need to have equity and not equality.
 - PPIE input - need to build in more input and hours to give people time.
 - More inclusive MLTC research
 - Who we talk to and participate
 - Taxi issue - not claiming back.
 - Need to think about excluded groups. Polish is the second most spoken language.
 - people's presumptions about the most spoken languages.
 - Equality Impact Assessments.
 - Access to translators.
 - Challenges and barriers
 - Language - need to speak plain English.

- Researcher training.
- Easy reading does not mean accessible.
- The pace needs to be slower.
- Mechanisms for sharing best practices
- Guidance documents
- Video
- Show not tell
- Resources that can be used outside of AIMS
- Posters
- Role Play
- PPIE doing the posters.
- Feeding into training.
- The PPIE future involvement.